

FACTORS AND METHODS USED FOR EVALUATION OF E-LEARNING

Jeo Joy A.

Associate Professor, Department of Computer Science, Kristu Jayanti College (Autonomous),
Bengaluru.

e-mail: jeojoya@gmail.com

Abstract

E-learning is gaining rapid momentum in the modern higher education sector. The different modes of E-learning content involving impressive tools such as AV, AR and VR have definitely attracted users from every walk of life towards it. The enormous benefits and open accessibility of this arena have definitely added value base for the same. From the historical perspective of supplementary role towards core credit earning course highlights the pivotal role it plays in the modern higher education era. Of age various queries have popped out on the quality they impart on the beneficiaries. Together various models and tools have nurtured for the evaluation of the same. This paper gives information about the various factors and methods used for the evaluation of E-learning.

Keywords: E-learning, Evaluation, LMS, MOOC

1. INTRODUCTION

E-learning is the buss word which supplements other teaching pedagogies available in the modern education sector. Easy accessibility and better internet connectivity have paved way for its manifold growth. Various Universities and autonomous institutions have initiated imbibing credits earned through e-learning as part of their academic credits.

E-Learning is one of the areas which attracts research and development funds. In order to make this investment in an effective manner robust models of evaluation are necessary. The report on Leonardo da Vinci programme, one of the largest sponsors of innovative e-learning projects also identified lack of systematic evaluation. The major concern with most of the e-learning projects is that they are focused solely with monitoring and evaluation, and in this perspective the major focus is on input elements or the total number of learners trained against the total outputs (successfully completed learners) or the impact it created on the professional development of the learner.

In any e-learning process evaluation is often found as the weakest area. The main reason may be non-availability of standards against which evaluation to be done. Other reasons may be

- Outcome not defined
- Purpose may not have been determined
- Beneficiaries are not clearly identified
- No definite goal or objective stated for the programme
- Evaluation process was designed after programme commenced
- Scarce of resources for evaluation
- Higher attrition rates may proclaim evaluation process unreliable
- Requirement of measures instead of standardized tests
- Diversity among the learners

- Nonuniformity in start schedule and implementation stage

According to Ozkan and others there are forty-six different LMS success criteria [1] for evaluation which are in turn grouped into six main categories such as Technical Issues on System Quality (Eight Criteria), Technical Issues on Service Quality(Six Criteria), Technical Issues on Content Quality(Fourteen Criteria), Social Issues based on Learner Perspective(Five Criteria), Social Issues on Instructor Attitudes(Nine Criteria) and Supporting Issues(Four Criteria). In the evaluation of e-learning only five major clusters of variables have emerged [1] and they are

Individual Learner Variables: Physical attributes of the learner.

Learning Environment Variables: Physical, organizational and subject environments

Contextual Variables: Socio-economic factors, political context, cultural background and geographic location

Technology Variables: Software, hardware, connectivity, the media and mode of delivery

Pedagogical Variables: Level and nature of learner support systems, accessibility issues, methodologies, flexibility, learner autonomy, selection and recruitment, assessment and examination, and accreditation and certification

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

As a result of the ¹E-VAL project which took place between 2002 and 2005 a number of new models and tools were developed for the evaluation of e-learning. They fall under two categories: First category which has basically online data gathering tools for assessing (e.g. student perception questionnaires) and second which uses instruments for recording and analyzing duration of usage and frequency of log-in, total number of pages accessed and so on.

2.1 Kirkpatrick's Four Levels of Evaluation [2]

This four-level model can be implemented in technology-based e-learning as well, in addition to the traditional learning methodologies. Here each successive evaluation level is built upon incrementally with the help of information provided by the lower level. This model always starts with Level I(Reactions) and then moves up sequentially to Level II(Learning) then Level III(Transfer) and ends with Level IV(Results).

Level I (Reactions)

This level also known as smilesheet measures the perceptions and reactions of the participants on the likeness of the training provided and the relevance of the course material provided. According to Kirkpatrick evaluation at this level is mandatory for the improvement of every programme.

Level II(Learning)

This level measures the amount of learning occurred during the programme through pre-test(test conducted before training) and post-test(test conducted after training). Methods used in this level varies from formal to informal testing, team assessment and self-assessment.

Level III(Transfer)

This level measures the knowledge transfer that has occurred among the learners in the due course of the programme. This level answers the questions such as whether the acquired skill or knowledge is used in everyday environment of the learner. From the trainer's point of view this level gives the best assessment of a programme's effectiveness.

Level IV(Results)

¹ "A Guide to the Evaluation of e-learning", Europe Handbook Series Volume 2, ISSN 1610-0875 2006

This level measures the effectiveness of the programme based on end results. From a business training perspective, it can be increased production, improved quality, decreased cost, increased sales, increased profit or return on investment.

2.2 Clusters of Evaluation as per Fitzpatrick [1]

Objectives oriented evaluation approaches [3]

Here the evaluation process should ascertain, whether the purposes, goals and targets have actually been achieved – and if not narrate the reasoning for the same. It is otherwise referred as goal-driven evaluation.

Management Oriented Evaluation Approaches

These approaches serve decision makers and hence the focus of evaluation will be as per the needs of managers, policy-makers, administrators and practitioners.

Consumer Oriented Evaluation Approaches

This approach is considered to be summative, rather than formative and its primary focus is on evaluation of the product. It relies heavily on techniques for criteria referenced evaluation such as benchmarking or kite marking. This approach is prominent among standard's agencies and watchdog organizations.

Expertise Oriented Evaluation Approaches

This approach solely based on the notion of "connoisseurship" and criticism relies predominantly on the subjective professional judgement and expert knowledge of the assessor. It can be formal or informal, based on individual expertise or, on the collective expertise of a panel. It does not rely much on external tools and instruments instead relies more on the experience level and knowledge of the evaluator.

Participant Oriented Evaluation Approaches

This is a primary approach where the participants of the project are considered as the starting point. For example, an educational project for women returners include the learners, the project staff, the management team and the funders. In addition, it can expand it to the wider community comprising of the learner's families, the schools attended by the learners' children, childcare agencies and so on. Hence in this approach the numerous sub-groups involved share all or some of the above characteristics including responsive evaluation, naturalistic evaluation, utilization focused evaluation and empowerment evaluation.

Learning Orientated Evaluation Approaches

This is a novice approach and was the odd one out in Fitzpatrick's classification. The basic working principle of this approach states that the purpose of evaluation should in one way or other contribute to collective or organizational learning. Different models developed under this approach are based on distinct theories and types of learning include corrective or behavioural learning, cognitive learning and social learning. Here the inputs of the learning are the outputs and processes of the evaluation.

2.3 Qualitative E-Learning Assessment Methods²

Task-Based Simulations

Simulations are real-life virtual environments created for testing the practical and application level knowledge of the learner. This helps the e-learner to equip themselves with all the armors required to face the actual real-life circumstances and experiences with the help of a risk-free virtual reality environment. In order to make the virtual reality environment resemble the real-life scenario the auxiliary effects of audio and graphics settings are used.

Branching Scenarios

Here the online learners are provided with various decision gateways which lead them into

² Christopher Pappas "E Learning Design and Development" October 4, 2016.

different routes ahead. The decision gateways help the learner to converge towards the desired outcome. As this method involves many decision gateways it is always prudent to have a narrative e-Learning storyboard in place before implementation of this methodology.

Online Group Collaboration Projects with Feedback

This mechanism derives its base from the peer-based e-learning concept which caters feedback from the learners in order to perceive qualitative information. Here e-learners are divided into groups and each one is assigned a problem to be solved. Once the outcome is attained the groups can have an online presentation about the same. It can be implemented by providing a checklist or questionnaire to the e-learners for completion during the e-learning assignment. Afterwards make the e-learners themselves to assess the performance of their peers. For the smoother running of the process develop and circulate the group guidelines well in advance and make them aware that they are being assessed.

Open-Ended Questions

Open-Ended Questions are those which does not pave way for right or wrong answers. Here the e-learner has to draw conclusions on the field of study. The drawback of this methodology is that grading is a distant reality. However, a rubric can be developed in advance to streamline the process which in turn helps in the compilation of accurate data.

Problem-Solving Case Studies

This technique nurtures e-learners into critical minds or detectives which helps them to solve problems. The technique involves a case study or real-world example where e-learners provide the solutions. The solution should be substantiated with the explanation of the route map towards the solution. E-learners can complement it with the narration stating why they consider this solution as the optimal one.

E-Learning Blogs

Motivate e-learners to set up an e-learning blog and post on a daily or weekly basis. There should be a posting schedule that includes prompts or questions, minimum word count, and deadlines for the upload. These blogs can be reviewed periodically for assessing the progress of e-learner and suggestions for improvement can be provided. Free blogging platforms are always prudent to start with. Additional online tutorials can be created for new bloggers in order to minimize the learning time frame.

Online Interviews

Online interviews are made possible through video conferencing and webinars which can be applicable for smaller groups or individuals which in turn helps in the mentoring process. Here questions are prepared in advance and an online interview is scheduled with each e-learner. During the process e-learners can express their concerns and provide feedback. Motivate the e-learner to identify their strengths and weaknesses, and then suggest alternative e-learning resources for their improvement. Even oral viva is made possible with these means.

Forums and Online Discussions

This creates a platform for e-learners to share vivid ideas, explore new topics, and improve their comprehension at large. It also creates fruitful online discussions which in turn reveal the level of understanding of the e-learner. Instructors can monitor the online discussion by posting prompts and popping out thought-provoking questions at random periods of time.

2.4 Performance Indicators in e Learning³

- Sessions vs. Total Users: Checks for the frequency of session users.

³www.elucidat.com/the-top-10-elearning-analytics-stats-to-track

- **Completion Rate:** Checks whether all registered linear e-learning users persist as active e-learners till the end. If the e-learners are given the option of going through a range of performance topics check which topic is visited the most and by whom.
- **User Statistics:** Does the e-learning project gets the expected count and domain of audience. What is the demand ratio? If the enrollment is not up to the target do you need to implement any marketing strategies.
- **Device Type:** Nature of devices used and whether they are apt for the e-learning design paradigm. Whether any enhancements to be made to make it more mobile-friendly?
- **Session Times:** This indicator checks for the optimum length of a session for the distinct topic as per the nature of the topic.
- **Poll results:** This indicator checks the inference obtained from the polls regarding user attitudes, preconceptions or beliefs. Whether these inferences to be addressed ahead of learning.
- **Tricky Questions:** Factors like discrimination index tells about the questions where users find more difficulty in giving the right answer. Whether the delivery of the content to be modified or take up other measures to help these e-learners.
- **Easy Questions:** Which are the questions that the users are getting the right answers (ninety to hundred percentage) in the first attempt itself? Whether these questions are intentionally made as a part of evaluation or should change be made to increase the difficulty level of the questions.
- **Drop Off:** Check for the pages where maximum number of users drop off is happening and analyze the reason for this. Reasons can be page errors, lower engagement, less relevant content, navigation or UX issues, or perhaps they simply have all that they need and the rest can be discarded.
- **User navigation:** If branching scenario decision gateways are provided which branching does majority of the users proceed. What inference does this imply about their needs, behaviors or profiles?

2.5 Emerging Areas in e Learning – An Indian Context

Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology, India has identified the following new areas as emerging areas in e-Learning⁴:

- Development of a framework for qualitative online testing
- Development of a framework/standard for quality assessment of e-Learning content
- Development of Simulations, Interactive Experiments including 3D Labs
- Development of mobile compatible e-content packaging and delivery systems
- Personalized e-Learning
- Learning Analytics i.e. measurement, collection, analysis and reporting of data about learners and their contexts.

⁵According to a report by KPMG, the Indian online education industry will register a 6X growth in 2021. From 1.6 million users in 2016, it will grow to 9.6 million users by 2021. It will also be worth \$1.96 billion. Projections show that the e-learning market worldwide is

⁴ <https://meity.gov.in/content/e-learning>

⁵ www.indiatoday.in/education-today/featurephilia/story/how-online-learning-is-doing-away-with-traditional-learning-methods-1382923-2018-11-05

forecast to surpass 243 billion US dollars by 2022. ⁶India's e-learning market is the second largest after the US and is expected to grow by 15.64 percent and exceed \$48 billion by 2020.

2.5 MOOCs and Assessment Methods

[M] The first course called MOOC took place in 2011. It is basically categorized as xMOOC and cMOOC. The basic aim of xMOOC is on content and transmission of information while the cMOOC focuses on interaction. Formative assessment in xMOOC is usually done with multiple choice questions and delivering tasks. But in the case of cMOOC summative assessment is done through peer assessment. The basic attribute of an xMOOC is that it is scalable which refers to the ability of the system to skilfully manage a growing amount of work. From the teacher's point of view MOOC, especially xMOOC offer reliable measurement of the field of knowledge which can be accompanied by feedback mechanism in order to reinforce the learning content. The main drawback of MOOC lies in the benchmarking criteria of passing the test for certification. Studies reveal the fact that learners received fair grades and usual feedback in the peer assessment of cMOOC. Another factor worth noting in the study is that the grades awarded by a group of facilitators are not significantly different from those given by the learners in the peer assessment. Peer assessment may work well for blog entries and discussion forums. The main drawback of peer assessment especially when they are in the hands of learners is that they create their own rules and policies on the basis of criteria which are not clearly defined. Another issue with this type of assessment is that learner assumes themselves as experts which paves the way for mistaken opinions such as considering other learners too as experts. With huge number of learners in the MOOC platform assessment through software is the fair option.

2.5.1 Alternative ways of Assessment in MOOC [5]

Peer Assessment 2.0

Here the peer assessment process is supervised by experts which eliminates the drawbacks of the former methodology. According to the state of learning and the participant's context tasks can be associated with the peer assessment.

Network-Based Grading

Learners are not assessed based on their individual work rather according to a network metric.

Portfolio [6]

Portfolios gives an understanding of the learner's learning process which can be well associated with feedback.

Mantle of the Expert

This methodology groups learners who are adjudged as expert assessors in the field. This group can negotiate their expectations with other groups of assessors where a teacher will be acting as a facilitator.

Semantic Web

This allows students to perform assessment tests through semantic web and ontologies and in turn receives the feedback.

Learning Analytics

This is defined as the process of measuring, collecting, analysing and communicating data about learners and their contexts with the purpose of understanding and optimising learning in the context in which it takes place.

3. Observations and Conclusion

The observations made with MOODLE LMS for a sample of ninety-two under graduate

⁶ www.aurumequity.com/the-online-education-industry-in-india-present-and-future

learners while conducting test on thirty multiple choice questions is given below in the way of Discrimination Index and Facility Index.

From the observation we can get useful information on the discrimination level of the learner sample and the difficulty level of the questions.

The graph below depicts the grading level report of an online evaluation test conducted on under graduate students on a value added course.

From the graph we can observe the understanding level of the learners.

The massive group of e-learners are increasing enormously on a day to day basis and with the advent of modern tools available for evaluation is definitely standardizing the entire process. The study does the comparative analysis of various tools and methods available and highlighted the pros and cons of each methodology. Hybrid models for evaluation of e-learning with more efficiency is the focus of future development.

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